

LOOPER

LEARNING LOOPS IN THE PUBLIC REALM

WP5. Learning Living Lab – Brussels

T5.2. Participatory data collection and visualisation

Deliverable D 5.2a

REPORT ON THE OUTCOMES OF THE PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION PHASE

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

Problem identification is a key phase in the learning loops that are at the core of the LOOPER Living Labs. This phase seeks to engage residents of the area covered by the Living Labs in surfacing problems in the public realm and coming to understand those problems more deeply in order to address them.

The Brussels LOOPER Living Lab is located in the municipality of Schaerbeek in the north of the Brussels Capital Region. This municipality has many issues regarding mobility and is therefore an interesting testing ground for the LOOPER co-creation methodology. VUB-MOBI has partnered with citizen NGO BRAL to try to identify and address issues of concern in the Helmet district in Schaerbeek.

The problem identification phase began in February 2018 with a blank page, i.e. open to all sorts of suggestions in terms of problems experienced by the citizens. The process started with a public meeting and ended with a data collection campaign in September 2018. During two meetings in the spring of 2018, citizens identified traffic safety as an urgent problem in the neighbourhood. Input from these meetings was supplemented with input from encounters with citizens at local markets.

Once traffic safety became the topic of the Living Lab, the discussion continued to which data should be collected to prove there is a problem with traffic safety in the area. A third citizen meeting was organised to find out what exactly citizens wanted to measure about traffic safety. Three themes were identified: speed of cars, use of the road and public space, and car pressure.

A data collection campaign was set up by BRAL and VUB-MOBI to collect data on traffic safety. This campaign included a survey about the mobility preferences of residents, a geotagging application through which citizens could identify traffic safety hotspots, and pop-up field research to count traffic and measure the speed of cars. This data collection campaign was quite successful: the survey was completed by over 100 citizens, around 20 citizens attended in the pop-up field research, and ten people used the geotagging tool despite difficulties with registering and adding data.

The data collected during this stage of the LOOPER co-creation process was used to inform citizens and the municipality of the problems in the area, as well as a base from which solutions can be co-designed. The traffic count showed that small vehicles such as passenger cars and pedestrians account for most traffic in the area; large vehicles and cyclists are only a minority. During the speed measurement, one-third of all measured vehicles was driving over the speed limit of 30 km/h.

Although traffic safety was a very hot topic in Schaerbeek, the Living Lab organisers encountered difficulties in setting up a Living Lab that was truly carried by local citizens. One of the explanations of this could be that a few weeks before the Brussels Living Lab kicked off, a traffic safety initiative called 1030/0 was founded by Schaerbeek citizens that were concerned about traffic safety. The participants of the LOOPER Living Lab overlapped with the citizens in 1030/0, and citizens seemed to prefer to deal with the topic in their own organisation rather than in the external LOOPER project. Moreover, citizens may also have been sceptical about LOOPER since the organisers could not guarantee that the efforts from citizens would result in concrete actions by the local government.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Objective of D5.2a

The objective of this deliverable is to describe and summarise the outcomes of the problem identification phase in the first loop of the LOOPER Living Lab in Brussels. This document is based on information from deliverable 5.1 on the Brussels Living Lab implementation plan as well as input from the logbook in which all Living Lab meetings in Brussels are logged.

1.2. Related deliverables

Deliverable 5.2a is a preliminary report that will be finalised as deliverable 5.2b during the second loop in month 29 (November 2019). Deliverable 5.2a is preceded by the Brussel Living Lab implementation plan (deliverable 5.1) and followed by the report on the co-design and evaluation outcomes (deliverable 5.3a). Similar deliverables will be written about the LOOPER Living Labs in Verona and Manchester in work packages 6 and 7, respectively.

The report on the data collection procedure framework (deliverable 2.2) and the guidelines for implementing urban living labs (deliverable 4.1) are also linked to this report on the outcomes of the problem identification phase in the Brussels LOOPER Living Lab.

2. FRAMING AS PLANNED IN D5.1

2.1. The Living Lab

The Brussels Living Lab is located in Helmet, a neighbourhood in the municipality of Schaerbeek (Dutch: Schaarbeek) in the north of Brussels (see Figure 1). The area was selected because it contains some of Schaerbeek's traffic safety hotspots such as the Chaussée de Haecht that leads from the suburbs directly into Helmet as well as the Chaussée de Helmet, which is a busy street with shops, trams, cars, and cyclists.

Figure 1 The location of the Brussels LOOPER Living Lab

Helmet is a diverse neighbourhood with an individual character and many independent well-established shops along its central high street, the “Helmetsesteenweg/Chaussée de Helmet”. The neighbourhood’s population has grown by 24% over the past decade and its population density is more than double the Brussels average. One-third of the population is non-Belgian, of which more than half come from European Union member states. A more detailed description of the Brussels LOOPER Living Lab can be found in deliverable 5.1¹.

2.2. Data collection plan

2.2.1. Defining the problem

When the Brussels Living Lab was set up, the Living Lab organisers held meetings with Schaerbeek municipality and the regional Brussels Mobility administration. Together with input from the network of the implementation partner BRAL, the following possible problems were suggested:

- Traffic safety on the high street
- Safer streets for children that go to schools along the high street
- Accessibility of Park Huart Hamoir
- Underutilisation of Schaerbeek train station
- Air quality
- Noise caused by air planes
- Preventing the destruction of a small park (Square Riga) because of a new metro line
- ‘Saving’ tram line 55/32, which could disappear when the metro is finished

During two workshops on 13 February and 25 February 2018, discussions were held on what problem would be the topic of the Brussels LOOPER Living Lab. As the suggestions above show, mobility is an important topic to residents. During the third LOOPER workshop on 9 May 2018, potential data collection ideas on three traffic safety topics were discussed with citizens: speeding cars; places where people gather; and the amount of public space dedicated to modes of transport. The suggested types of data to be collected for the three topics are summarised in Table 1.

SPEEDING

¹ [http://looperproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/LOOPER_D5.1 Brussels Living Lab Implementation Plan.pdf](http://looperproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/01/LOOPER_D5.1_Brussels_Living_Lab_Implementation_Plan.pdf)

<p>Reduce traffic speed and illegal parking:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Survey residents about their perception of traffic safety • Measure speeds before and after the implementation of the 30 km/h zone in Schaerbeek in September 2018. 	<p>Survey about citizens' perception of traffic safety.</p> <p>(Mobile) speed measurement devices.</p>
PLACE WHERE PEOPLE GATHER	
<p>Who goes to which destinations in Helmet and why?</p>	<p>Talk to people on the street.</p>
AMOUNT OF PUBLIC SPACE	
<p>Parked cars:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How long do they remain parked? • Where do the cars come from (what street/municipality) 	<p>Parking tickets and scan car.</p>
<p>Use of different modes of transport in the area:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measure the speed and route take per mode of transport 	<p>Mobile application</p>
<p>Unsafe roads:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Add category 'unsafe roads' to the existing FixMyStreet application 	<p>Mobile application</p>

Table 1 Possible data to be collected in the Brussels Living Lab

3. DATA COLLECTION METHODOLOGY

3.1. Campaign

After the third LOOPER workshop, VUB-MOBI and BRAL developed a concrete data collection plan² in order to communicate clearly what is expected from citizens. Citizens could contribute to the data collection campaign in three ways: fill in a survey on traffic safety; use the geotagging tool to indicate spots where traffic is unsafe; and help collect data on traffic volume and speed during one of the pop-up field researches.

Based on the input from citizens, the data collection campaign focused on the following aspects:

- What are the mobility preferences of citizens? (survey)
- Where are unsafe spots in the neighbourhood according to citizens? (geotagging tool)
- How fast do cars drive? (field research)
- How many cars/bikes/pedestrians use the streets in Helmet? (field research)
- Which destinations in the area are frequented by many people and how do they get there? (field research)

The data collection campaign thus consisted of a subjective part and an objective part. Through the identification of unsafe spots in the neighbourhood and the survey data about the *impressions* of citizens was collected, whereas the field research was used to collect objective data on traffic safety.

3.2. Data

Between June and August 2018, citizens could indicate using the online geotagging tool where are unsafe spots in the area and comment on traffic safety in their neighbourhood via a survey. In September 2018, citizens participated in traffic counts, speed measurements using a mobile radar, and an origin-destination survey. This data was presented on the LOOPER website³ and LOOPER Facebook page⁴ and was presented at subsequent meetings with citizens.

3.2.1. Survey

A survey (see Annex 1 – Survey citizens) was sent out to all LOOPER participants and distributed by Living Lab organisers and citizens to 1000 houses in the Helmet neighbourhood. The survey contained questions on people's preferences regarding mobility in Helmet, whether traffic safety is an issue in their street or in their neighbourhood, at what time cars speed, which measures people support the most to increase traffic safety, and at which place an intervention is necessary. In order to increase the response rate, two tickets to the local mini golf were given to one of the participants. 107 people filled in the survey.

3.2.2. Geotagging

The geotagging tool⁵ was promoted as an application through which citizens could indicate where road users drive too fast. Ten people requested an account to add data; data from citizens received during the workshops was added to the application from our own accounts. Since account

² <http://brussels.looperproject.eu/de-datacollectie-is-begonnen/>

³ <http://brussels.looperproject.eu/visualisation/>

⁴ <https://www.facebook.com/looper.helmet/>

⁵ <https://www.loopertagging.eu/brussels/>

registration was not automated, a tutorial⁶ was written for users on how to create an account and how to add data to the tool.

3.2.3. Field research

The field research campaign took place on four occasions in September 2018:

- Tuesday 4 September from 07:30 until 09:00
- Thursday 6 September from 18:00 until 20:00
- Tuesday 11 September from 18:00 until 20:00
- Wednesday 12 September from 14:00 until 16:00

Tuesday and Thursday evening were chosen as this is the most 'normal' rush hour in Brussels. Wednesday afternoon was chosen because schools are out earlier than usual, thereby generating more traffic in the afternoon. The 17 different measurement locations were based on previous input from citizens as well as on input from citizens that participated in the data collection.

The first data collection occasion on 4 September was not open to the public because VUB-MOBI and BRAL wanted to see which places would be most interesting to research and needed to test the application to count modes of transport and the mobile speed measurement device.

Figure 2 The mobile speed radar used for data collection

The application CounterPoint (for traffic counts) was used during the closed data collection occasion on 4 September but was not used during the other occasions due to problems with installing it on mobile devices from participants. It was therefore decided that the traffic speed measurements and traffic counts would be done using paper and manually digitalised. The forms used for data collected can be found in Annex 2 – Traffic counts and Annex 3 – Speed measurements.

The data collected during the field research campaign includes:

⁶ <http://brussels.looperproject.eu/geotagging/>

4. 20 COUNTS OF NUMBER AND TYPE OF VEHICLES (LARGE VEHICLES SUCH AS BUSES AND TRUCKS; SMALL VEHICLES SUCH AS PASSENGER CARS AND CARGO VANS; BIKES; PEDESTRIANS) IN ONE OR BOTH DIRECTIONS OF TRAFFIC PER 15 MINUTES. IN TOTAL, 4 105 ROAD USERS WERE COUNTED IN 17 LOCATIONS (SEE ANNEX 1 – SURVEY CITIZENS)

Welke van de onderstaande aspecten hebben jouw persoonlijke voorkeur met betrekking tot mobiliteit in Helmet? Geef max. 4 antwoorden.

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Snel mijn bestemming bereiken | <input type="checkbox"/> Veilige straten waar kinderen kunnen spelen |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Veilig mijn bestemming bereiken | <input type="checkbox"/> Minder geluidsoverlast |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Fietspaden en -stallingen in de buurt | <input type="checkbox"/> Meer groen |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Parkeerplaatsen dichtbij mijn huis | <input type="checkbox"/> Betere luchtkwaliteit |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Parkeerplaatsen dichtbij winkels en diensten (bank, dokter, postkantoor...) | <input type="checkbox"/> Gemakkelijke toegang tot openbaar vervoer |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> Andere: _____ |

Ik vind dat verkeersveiligheid een probleem is in Helmet.

Volledig mee oneens 1 2 3 4 5 Volledig mee eens

Overdreven snelheid is een probleem in mijn straat.

Volledig mee oneens 1 2 3 4 5 Volledig mee eens

Naam van mijn straat (huisnummer optioneel):

Overdreven snelheid is een probleem in mijn straat, vooral op dit tijdstip:

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Ochtendpiek (8u-10u) | <input type="checkbox"/> 's Avonds (19u-22u) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Overdag (10u-16u) | <input type="checkbox"/> 's Nachts (22hu-6u) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Avondpiek (16u-19u) | <input type="checkbox"/> In het weekend |

Indien je €10.000 zou mogen investeren in mobiliteit, welke maatregelen zou je willen uittesten? Kies maximaal 4 opties:

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Betere oversteekplaatsen voor voetgangers | <input type="checkbox"/> Meer verkeersdrempels |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Het aantal parkeerplaatsen of -garages verhogen | <input type="checkbox"/> Meer snelheidscontroles door de politie |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Het aantal parkeerplaatsen of -garages verminderen | <input type="checkbox"/> Meer plaats voor voetgangers |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Sensibiliseringscampagnes rond veilig rijden | <input type="checkbox"/> Meer fietspaden |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Panelen en andere visuele hulpmiddelen om traag rijden aan te moedigen | <input type="checkbox"/> Andere: _____ |

Waar (straat of kruispunt) is er, volgens jou, een dringende interventie nodig en waarom?

Wens je nog iets toe te voegen omtrent verkeersveiligheid in jouw wijk?

- Ja, ik wil meedoen aan de wedstrijd voor 2 tickets voor de Josaphat minigolf
- Ja, hou me op de hoogte over de toekomstige acties omtrent verkeersveiligheid in Helmet!

Mijn naam:

Mijn e-mail:

Mijn GSM nummer:

QUESTIONNAIRE

Pour le(s)quel(s) des aspects ci-dessous avez-vous une préférence en matière de mobilité à Helmet ? Choisissez max. 4 réponses.

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Atteindre ma destination rapidement | <input type="checkbox"/> Des rues où les enfants peuvent jouer en toute sécurité |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Atteindre ma destination en toute sécurité | <input type="checkbox"/> Réduire les nuisances sonores |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Des pistes cyclables et parking vélo | <input type="checkbox"/> Améliorer la qualité de l'air |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Des places de parking près de chez moi | <input type="checkbox"/> Plus d'espaces verts |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Des places de parking près des commerces ou services (banque, docteur,...) | <input type="checkbox"/> Des transports en communs accessibles |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> Autre: _____ |

Je trouve que la sécurité routière est un problème à Helmet.

Pas du tout d'accord 1 2 3 4 5 Tout à fait d'accord

La vitesse excessive est un problème dans ma rue.

Pas du tout d'accord 1 2 3 4 5 Tout à fait d'accord

Nom de ma rue (numéro optionnel)

La vitesse excessive est un problème dans ma rue, surtout à ce moment-ci :

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Heures de pointe du matin (8h-10h) | <input type="checkbox"/> Le soir (19h-22h) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> En journée (10h-16h) | <input type="checkbox"/> La nuit (22h-6h) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Heures de pointe du soir (16h-19h) | <input type="checkbox"/> Le week-end |

Si vous aviez 10.000€ à investir dans la mobilité, quelles mesures ci-dessous aimeriez-vous tester? Max. 4 choix :

- De meilleurs passages piétons
- Augmenter le nombre de parkings ou de garages
- Diminuer le nombre de parkings ou de garages
- Des campagnes pour sensibiliser à une conduite plus sûre
- Des casse-vitesse
- Des panneaux de signalisation ou autres visuels pour encourager une vitesse réduite
- Plus de contrôle policier pour assurer le respect des limitations de vitesse
- Plus de place pour les piétons
- Plus de pistes cyclables
- Autre : _____

Indiquez un endroit (rue ou carrefour) où une intervention urgente est nécessaire et pourquoi ?

Autre chose à signaler par rapport à la sécurité routière dans votre quartier ?

- Oui, je veux participer au concours et tenter de gagner les deux tickets pour le minigolf Josaphat
- Oui, tenez-moi au courant des futures actions en matière de sécurité routière à Helmet !

Mon nom :

Mon e-Mail :

Mon numéro de téléphone :

- Annex 2 – Traffic counts).
- Speed of vehicles in km/h in six different places. Using the Bushnell Velocity speed gun, the speed of 484 out of 618 counted vehicles was measured. The device does not correctly measure speed below 20 km/h (see Annex 3 – Speed measurements).

A more detailed description of the data collection activities can be found in the following section.

5. RESULTS OF THE PARTICIPATORY DATA COLLECTION

5.1.1. Citizens' opinion on mobility

Data on the mobility preferences of citizens were collected using an online survey. The results were published on the LOOPER website⁷. According to the respondents, the five most important mobility preferences are improving air quality, reaching a destination safely, cycling infrastructure, reducing noise pollution, and safe streets where children can play (see Figure 3).

Figure 3 Top 5 mobility preferences citizens

Citizens could also indicate how they experience traffic safety in the Helmet neighbourhood and in their own street. Of the 98 respondents, 79% indicated that traffic safety is a problem in Helmet, and 72% believed cars drive too fast in their street. Figure 4 shows in which streets citizens believe speeding is a problem and in which it is not (red indicates speeding is a problem, green indicates speeding is not a problem).

⁷ <http://brussels.looperproject.eu/visualisation/#enquete>

Figure 4 Responses to the statement 'speeding is a problem in my street'

Speeding was found to be mostly a problem in the evening between 19:00 and 22:00 and at night (see Figure 5).

Figure 5 Times at which citizens believe cars speed the most

When asked how they would spend €10.000 to improve traffic safety, citizens indicated that they would like more speed checks by the police (23%), followed by more bike paths (18%), and more speed bumps (16%) (see Figure 6).

Figure 6 How to spend €10.000 on mobility

The Helmetsesteenweg, Demolderlaan, and Helmetplein were identified⁸ by citizens as streets in need of an intervention to improve traffic safety.

5.1.2. Tagging unsafe spots

The input from citizens that used the geotagging tool was published on the LOOPER website⁹ and is shown in Figure 7. Green indicates positive examples, red indicates places where traffic is perceived as unsafe. The data was divided into four categories: other, cars, public transport, and pedestrians. Most input concerned cars.

Three citizens submitted a total of ten data entries using their own logins. This low number can be explained by the rather complicated account registration process. The other 40 data entries were submitted by the Living Lab coordinators, who collected the data from citizens on the street or during workshops. The vast majority of data entries concerned cars: only two were submitted for 'other' and only one for public transport and pedestrians.

⁸ <http://brussels.looperproject.eu/visualisation/#interventie>

⁹ <http://brussels.looperproject.eu/visualisation/#Datavisualisatie>

Figure 7 Input from citizens on traffic safety

5.1.3. Traffic speed and volume

The data from the speed measurements and traffic counts were published on the LOOPER website¹⁰ and the LOOPER Facebook page. During the six speed measurements, 618 vehicles were counted and of 484 vehicles the speed was measured. Nearly all the vehicles of which the speed has not been measured were going under the speed limit because of a traffic jam. The results of the measurements are shown in Figure 8. One third of the counted vehicles drove too fast: on average between 4 and 8 km/h over the speed limit of 30 km/h. One in nine drivers drove faster than 36 km/h, the speed at which they would receive a fine.

¹⁰ <http://brussels.looperproject.eu/visualisation/#metingenopstraat>

Figure 8 Speed of vehicles during measurements

Cars and pedestrians were counted the most during the 20 traffic counts in 17 different places in Helmet. Just over half of the 4 105 road users was a small vehicle (car, van, motor cycle, moped) and 45% was a pedestrian. Cyclists accounted for 3% of the road users counted, and large vehicles for 1% (see Figure 9). An interesting result from the collected data was that there were fewer cyclists (in percentages) on the busy shopping street that connects Helmet with the rest of the city than there were on the surrounding, less busy streets.

Figure 9 Counted road users by type

Goal: Let the participants take ownership of the project and become pioneers. Define a mission and vision statement for the project. Participants laid the groundwork and can now take on reaching out to further expand the scope of participants.

Communication: All participants of the information session were invited and asked to transfer the invitation. We also used the same channels as for the information session.

Activity: Follow the Urban Living Lab Kit guidelines for a 1-day workshop to answer the following questions in groups of about 8:

- Why do we want an urban lab?
- Which tangible results do we wish to obtain?
- How does the city as a whole benefit from these results?
- Who do we need to involve?
- What do they get out of the lab?
- Where do we best position our lab as an organisation?
- Where do our lab activities take place?
- How do we communicate within and about our lab?
- How do we fund the activities of our lab?
- Which activities should our lab carry out in order to achieve this?
- Which key roles does our lab fulfil?
- What would we like to learn through our lab?
- How do we want to learn?
- How would we like to develop the urban lab in the long term?

Result: Attendance was very low as only two citizens showed up, so we did not work on these questions. However, we developed a “marketing’ plan in order to promote LOOPER. We also started a Trello board (see Figure 11 and Figure 12) in order to exchange information with participants. This tool was quickly replaced by a Facebook page, on request from participants of the Third Living Lab Workshop (07/06/18).

Figure 11 LOOPER Trello page

Figure 12 LOOPER Trello page

Experiences: We may have asked for too much when planning a six-hour activity on Sunday afternoon. Fewer and shorter meetings may prove more effective in engaging citizens.

6.1.3. Presence at local events and marketing activities

Goal: Promote LOOPER and invite people to follow and participate to our project, gather information about the main mobility problems in the neighbourhood

Communication: We developed a new flyer with a more detailed description of the project. The A0-printout of the neighbourhood was used as a conversation starter at local events.

Activities:

- Discussions with citizens at local market
- Discussions with mothers with immigration background at local kids' centre
- Flyer houses
- Distribute flyers at local events, for example: inauguration Square Apollo, events of the cultural center
- Distribute flyers at school doors

Figure 13 Discussing traffic safety with citizens on the street

Result: Traffic safety was selected as main problem to work on.

Experiences: Most interviewed people were eager to share their views on mobility and traffic safety in the neighbourhood. However, most of them were less enthusiastic when invited to participate to co-design workshops, mainly due to lack of time.

6.1.4. Second Living Lab Workshop (09/05/18,19h-21h)

Content: Presentation by the municipality about finished and on-going mobility and urban planning projects; discussion about data collection

Goal: Decide which data to collect.

Communication: As described in 5.1.3, we organized a more active communication campaign, meeting citizens ourselves at strategic places and events. This helped us to gather e-mails and phone numbers and start a contact list. We also asked every participant of the workshop to fill

out a contact sheet at the start of the workshop to add their contact details to the list. VUB and BRAL shared the information in their newsletter.

Activity: Table discussions on what we need to measure and know more about in order to improve road safety.

Result: Fifteen citizens attended this workshop. Three themes were selected: speed, use of the road and public space and car pressure

Figure 14 A LOOPER workshop

Experiences: For some citizens this was their first LOOPER workshop. Unfortunately, seven left during the break. The brainstorm with post-its seemed a simple but effective way to collect ideas. The theme 'public space and car pressure' was dropped by the Living Lab organisers after this meeting, since we could not find a way in which we could collect data on this in a participatory way.

6.1.5. Third Living Lab Workshop (07/06/18,19h-21h)

Content: What will LOOPER measure and when?

Goal: Develop a program of activities for summer

Communication: The contact list was the main communication channel used for this workshop as we tried to have regular participants. Local NGO's also continued to share our invitations.

Activity: The three themes were explained by the organisers. Florence presented data sources and data collection ideas for speeding; Mareile for places in Helmet where people gather; Jesse for the amount of public space dedicated to modes of transport. The attendants could then join one of the three themes and discuss potential data collection ideas in smaller groups, using a timeline.

Result: Eight citizens attended this workshop. A co-designed data collection campaign with a set of activities to organize from June to September was agreed on.

Figure 15 Planning during a LOOPER workshop

Experiences: This workshop was the first one with a concrete output, which made it even more interesting for participants. During this workshop, it was also decided to create a Facebook page to share all the information. This helped to involve participants in between workshops and keep them informed of updates and important announcements.

6.1.6. Research Pop-Ups

Goal: Collect data about speed and road use on three different days and times.

Communication: The Facebook group and the mailing list were actively used to communicate. At this point in the project, the Facebook page counted 35 people and the mailing list around 30 e-mails. Most articles linked to the LOOPER website, where all the information was shared in details and a dynamic timeline showed the evolution of the project. The municipality also published an article on their website¹¹.

In order to reach the target group, a Facebook Ads campaign was launched. The French post reached 6916 people, of which 168 active engagements. The Dutch post reached 1368 people, which translated into 12 engagements. However, only 3 people present at the pop-ups heard about the activity through this campaign.

Activities: It started out as a circle where Mareile shared the maps of existing data and the maps that will be produced. After this introduction, the group divided into smaller groups and started collecting different data:

- Speed of cars with a speed radar
- Traffic with pen and paper
- Qualitative feedback about the neighbourhood and travel behaviours with face-to-face interviews

¹¹ <https://www.schaarbeek.be/nl/onderzoek-verkeersveiligheid-helmet>

Next to these events, we also organized an online survey and gathered information with the geotagging tool. More than 100 citizens answered the online survey.

Results: Sixteen citizens participated in the three research pop-ups. All the results are available on the [LOOPER website](#)

Experiences: Citizens were very enthusiastic to measure speeds of car, count vehicles, or interview citizens about their travel behaviour. We initially wanted to count traffic with the [CounterPoint](#) app, but this did not work on some mobile devices so we chose for pen-and-paper counts. The data of the counts was interesting, but not very representative since it usually consisted of 15 to 45 minutes of counting.

6.1.7. Car-free Sunday event

Goal: Start gathering ideas for the implementation and communicate results field research.

Communication: Thanks to the survey, the mailing list gathered many extra e-mails, increasing the number of contacts to about 140 e-mails. The Facebook page counted 50 followers.

Activity: At a 'mobility market' during the annual car-free Sunday in Brussels, we showed the results of the data collection and gathered the first proposals for measures. We also invited everyone to come to the co-design workshops.

Figure 16 Meeting citizens during car free Sunday

Results: We talked to citizens using maps and print-outs of our results. Children were entertained with a LOOPER colouring exercise. This resulted in many people giving our stand a quick glance of the eye and approximately 10 more in-depth conversations about the project and about traffic safety.

Experiences: The car-free Sunday is an annual event on which children in Brussels roam the streets on their bikes. They were not interested in talking about boring things like traffic safety. Other citizens also seemed more eager to enjoy the sunshine than to engage in discussion about traffic safety. With stiff competition from other mobility initiatives – some of which were more interactive – this outreach moment did not feel very successful as we only had a handful of serious conversations about traffic safety where we would introduce the project. Moreover, none of the people met during this event came to a workshop.

6.2. Demographics

The Brussels LOOPER Living Lab set out to be an open and inclusive place where people from all walks of life could discuss the problems in their area. Throughout the workshops we noticed that mostly middle-class citizens, often Dutch-speaking (in a city where Dutch is a minority language), with a higher educational background and an interest in mobility were participating in the Living Lab.

A survey was sent out to all LOOPER participants to define the criteria and weights of the stakeholder group 'citizens' for the evaluation of co-designed solutions (which is described in detail in deliverable 5.3a). From the 37 respondents we gained the following insights:

- Most participants have a university background. All but three respondents held a university or a higher education degree.
- The average age is 42.
- More women than men participated in the survey.
- More than half of the respondents did not own a car.
- The mode of transport used most often by respondents was the bike, followed by public transport. Only 4 people used their car most often.

Our experiences from the workshops was also that women were more active in the living lab.

In order to reach hard-to-reach groups, we decided to:

- Participate in regular group discussions with mothers from a kids' centre in the neighbourhood. Most of the women have a non-Belgian background.
- Meet citizens at the local market, mostly attracting hard-to-reach groups

We also contacted other local NGO's working with hard-to-reach groups (centre for the elderly, social housing, neighbourhood centre, ...) but had no positive answer.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The problem identification phase of the Brussels LOOPER Living Lab ran from February until September 2018. During these months, three workshops were organised, three data collection opportunities were set up, a survey about people's opinions on mobility was held, and an online tool was launched through which citizens could submit data about traffic safety. The living lab organisers also took part in community events in order to engage with more citizens, many of which had not yet heard of the project.

The area in which the Brussels living lab is located was selected in 2017 because of its problems with traffic safety. After a fatal accident in November 2017, a citizen initiative for traffic safety called 1030/0 was set up in Schaerbeek. This was just two months before the living lab was launched in Brussels. In a way, 1030/0 was exactly what the LOOPER Living Lab intended to be: a citizen-led initiative that committed itself to improving traffic safety in the municipality. Since people's time is limited and not everyone wants to commit themselves to improving traffic safety (which is a task for the government according to many citizens), LOOPER and 1030/0 competed for the time of citizens who are interested in and engaged with traffic safety. And in the end, 1030/0 won.

In 2018, other citizens initiatives popped up throughout Brussels and in Schaerbeek. Another mobility-related initiative was Filter-Café-Filtré, which is a parent-led movement for cleaner air around elementary schools. This initiative resulted in the implementation of temporary street closures before and after school called school streets. Again, the target audience of LOOPER largely overlapped with those of other initiatives.

With hindsight, the timing of the problem identification phase should have been shorter. For many citizens, the problem in the area was already clear: traffic is unsafe. They did not need to spend three workshops on defining this obvious problem. Moreover, the goals or outcome of the Living

Lab were never communicated clearly, partly because the Living Lab organisers could not make any promises about how citizens' input would be used by the government.

Relatedly, the position of the municipality of Schaerbeek was rather ambivalent towards the project. Although civil servants from the municipality's mobility department joined several meetings, there was no sense of cooperation between LOOPER and the municipality. This lack of government engagement – who, in the end, decides whether an idea will be executed – may have reduced the appeal of the project to citizens.

In order to reach as many citizens as possible, online communication methods were also used during the problem identification phase. A Facebook group and page as well as a LOOPER mailing list was set up. Citizens also could participate online with a geotagging tool, although this was not used by many citizens. Offline communication took place with the dissemination of flyers and posters in the neighbourhood as well as speaking directly to citizens on the streets.

It is difficult to tell whether the problem identification phase of the Brussels LOOPER Living Lab was successful. What number of workshops and data collection campaigns is sufficient and how many citizens should be engaged? Nevertheless, workshops were held, and data was collected by citizens in order to progress with the project. If the aim of the LOOPER Living Lab was to be carried by citizens, this has not yet been the case. If the aim was to involve citizens in discussing traffic safety with other citizens and collecting data on this issue, then the Brussels Living Lab has succeeded.

8. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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9. ANNEX 1 – SURVEY CITIZENS

Welke van de onderstaande aspecten hebben jouw persoonlijke voorkeur met betrekking tot mobiliteit in Helmet? Geef max. 4 antwoorden.

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Snel mijn bestemming bereiken | <input type="checkbox"/> Veilige straten waar kinderen kunnen spelen |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Veilig mijn bestemming bereiken | <input type="checkbox"/> Minder geluidsoverlast |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Fietspaden en -stallingen in de buurt | <input type="checkbox"/> Meer groen |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Parkeerplaatsen dichtbij mijn huis | <input type="checkbox"/> Betere luchtkwaliteit |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Parkeerplaatsen dichtbij winkels en diensten
(bank, dokter, postkantoor...) | <input type="checkbox"/> Gemakkelijke toegang tot openbaar vervoer |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> Andere: _____ |

Ik vind dat verkeersveiligheid een probleem is in Helmet.

Volledig mee oneens 1 2 3 4 5 Volledig mee eens

Overdreven snelheid is een probleem in mijn straat.

Volledig mee oneens 1 2 3 4 5 Volledig mee eens

Naam van mijn straat (huisnummer optioneel):

Overdreven snelheid is een probleem in mijn straat, vooral op dit tijdstip:

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Ochtendpiek (8u-10u) | <input type="checkbox"/> 's Avonds (19u-22u) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Overdag (10u-16u) | <input type="checkbox"/> 's Nachts (22hu-6u) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Avondpiek (16u-19u) | <input type="checkbox"/> In het weekend |

Indien je €10.000 zou mogen investeren in mobiliteit, welke maatregelen zou je willen uittesten? Kies maximaal 4 opties:

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Betere oversteekplaatsen voor voetgangers | <input type="checkbox"/> Het aantal parkeerplaatsen of -garages verhogen |
|--|--|

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Het aantal parkeerplaatsen of -garages verminderen | <input type="checkbox"/> Meer snelheidscontroles door de politie |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Sensibiliseringscampagnes rond veilig rijden | <input type="checkbox"/> Meer plaats voor voetgangers |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Panelen en andere visuele hulpmiddelen om traag rijden aan te moedigen | <input type="checkbox"/> Meer fietspaden |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Meer verkeersdrempels | <input type="checkbox"/> Andere: _____ |

Waar (straat of kruispunt) is er, volgens jou, een dringende interventie nodig en waarom?

Wens je nog iets toe te voegen omtrent verkeersveiligheid in jouw wijk?

- Ja, ik wil meedoen aan de wedstrijd voor 2 tickets voor de Josaphat minigolf
- Ja, hou me op de hoogte over de toekomstige acties omtrent verkeersveiligheid in Helmet!

Mijn naam:

Mijn e-mail:

Mijn GSM nummer:

QUESTIONNAIRE

Pour le(s)quel(s) des aspects ci-dessous avez-vous une préférence en matière de mobilité à Helmet ? Choisissez max. 4 réponses.

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Atteindre ma destination rapidement | <input type="checkbox"/> Des rues où les enfants peuvent jouer en toute sécurité |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Atteindre ma destination en toute sécurité | <input type="checkbox"/> Réduire les nuisances sonores |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Des pistes cyclables et parking vélo | <input type="checkbox"/> Améliorer la qualité de l'air |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Des places de parking près de chez moi | <input type="checkbox"/> Plus d'espaces verts |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Des places de parking près des commerces ou services (banque, docteur,...) | <input type="checkbox"/> Des transports en communs accessibles |
| | <input type="checkbox"/> Autre: _____ |

Je trouve que la sécurité routière est un problème à Helmet.

Pas du tout d'accord 1 2 3 4 5 Tout à fait d'accord

La vitesse excessive est un problème dans ma rue.

Pas du tout d'accord 1 2 3 4 5 Tout à fait d'accord

Nom de ma rue (numéro optionnel)

La vitesse excessive est un problème dans ma rue, surtout à ce moment-ci :

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Heures de pointe du matin (8h-10h) | <input type="checkbox"/> Le soir (19h-22h) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> En journée (10h-16h) | <input type="checkbox"/> La nuit (22h-6h) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Heures de pointe du soir (16h-19h) | <input type="checkbox"/> Le week-end |

Si vous aviez 10.000€ à investir dans la mobilité, quelles mesures ci-dessous aimeriez-vous tester? Max. 4 choix :

- | | |
|--|--|
| <input type="checkbox"/> De meilleurs passages piétons | <input type="checkbox"/> Augmenter le nombre de parkings ou de garages |
|--|--|

- | | |
|--|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Diminuer le nombre de parkings ou de garages | <input type="checkbox"/> Plus de contrôle policier pour assurer le respect des limitations de vitesse |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Des campagnes pour sensibiliser à une conduite plus sûre | <input type="checkbox"/> Plus de place pour les piétons |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Des casse-vitesse | <input type="checkbox"/> Plus de pistes cyclables |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Des panneaux de signalisation ou autres visuels pour encourager une vitesse réduite | <input type="checkbox"/> Autre : _____ |

Indiquez un endroit (rue ou carrefour) où une intervention urgente est nécessaire et pourquoi ?

Autre chose à signaler par rapport à la sécurité routière dans votre quartier ?

- Oui, je veux participer au concours et tenter de gagner les deux tickets pour le minigolf Josaphat
- Oui, tenez-moi au courant des futures actions en matière de sécurité routière à Helmet !

Mon nom :

Mon e-Mail :

Mon numéro de téléphone :

10. ANNEX 2 – TRAFFIC COUNTS

Verkeerstelling

Locatie (exact adres)

Meting in richting van...

Datum

Start meting

Eind meting

Weersomstandigheden

Tijd	0 - 15 minuten	16 - 30 minuten	31 - 45 minuten	46 - 60 minuten
Voertuigen (klein) auto/busje; motor/brommer 				
Voertuigen (groot) vrachtwagen; bus/tram 				
Fietsers 				
Voetgangers 				

11. ANNEX 3 – SPEED MEASUREMENTS

Instructions pour les comptages de trafic et les mesures de vitesse

Objectif

L'objectif des comptages est de savoir combien et quels moyens de transport utilisent les rues du quartier Helmet, et à quelle vitesse ils conduisent. Avec l'aide de ces données, nous allons, plus tard cette année, proposer et mettre en œuvre des idées pour améliorer la sécurité routière à Helmet.

Journée et moment de l'analyse

Afin de s'assurer que les résultats des comptages soient représentatifs, nous allons compter et mesurer le trafic le mardi et le jeudi soir. L'heure de pointe du lundi soir est souvent plus longue que la moyenne. Elle est plus courte le mercredi et le vendredi. Nous comptons et mesurons également le mercredi après-midi, lorsque les écoles primaires ont une demi-journée.

Localisation

Les lieux de comptage et de mesure de la circulation sont basés sur l'apport des résidents lors des réunions, sur l'application LOOPER et les réponses à l'enquête sur la sécurité routière à Helmet.

Comptages

Het tellen van vervoersmiddelen gebeurt met intervallen van 15 minuten. **Tel de voertuigen en voetgangers die aan jouw kant van de straat passeren.** Fietsers en voertuigen gaan normaliter in één richting; voetgangers kunnen in beide richtingen lopen. Tel eerst de snelle weggebruikers en dan de langzame. We maken onderscheid tussen de volgende verkeersmiddelen:

- **Fietsers:** volwassene; kind; volwassene (passagier); kind (passagier); afwijkend formaat fiets (bijv. bakfiets)
- **Voetgangers:** volwassene; kind; kind in wandelwagen; visueel handicap; fysieke beperking; rolstoel; skateboards
- **Voertuigen (klein):** auto/busje; motor/brommer
- **Voertuigen (groot):** vrachtwagen; bus/tram

Metten

Een snelheidsmeting gebeurt ook met intervallen van 15 minuten en wordt uitgevoerd door twee personen: één meet de snelheid, de ander noteert deze. Mocht je van een voertuig de snelheid niet gemeten hebben, tel deze dan wel op het formulier! Hierdoor kunnen we het percentage snelheidsovertreders berekenen. Op het formulier is er ook ruimte om het aantal fietsers te turven, hoewel we van deze de snelheid niet meten.

Locatie (exact adres)
 Meting in richting
 Datum
 Start meting
 Eind meting
 Weersomstandigheden

Fietsers:

#	km/h
1	
2	
3	
4	
5	
6	
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13	
14	
15	
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